

DESCRIPTION OF THE CREATION OF ROMANTIC COMPOSERS IN PERFORMANCE OF THE PIANO

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Abstract: Description of works of romantic composers in piano performance.

Keyword: romanticism, composition, dynamics, rhythm, texture.

Romanticism is a trend that appeared in the literature and art of Europe and America in the first half of the 18th and 19th centuries and spread throughout the world. Romanticism is derived from the Spanish word "romance", which originally referred to a lyrical and heroic song, and later to large epic works about knights.

The adjective "Romantic" began to be used in the 17th century to refer to works written in the Romance languages, imbued with the spirit of adventure and heroism. English writers and literary critics used the word in the 18th century to discuss the literature of the Middle Ages and Renaissance. Ferenc Liszt's "Petrarchian sonnets" are important because they embody programmatic and romantic lines.

Liszt uses tremolo, chordal trills in his works for piano made extensive use of orchestral styles such as cadence in the upper register Excellent use of the clear and crisp explanation in the article positional complexes (okawa, chords) in Liszt piano music. The use of jumps was a novelty, they have a huge range of sound and gives majesty.

One and only across the entire keyboard Liszt's octave double-note passage played on the pedal can be included among the favorite techniques.

In Liszt's piano works, there are nine Hungarians rhapsodies occupy one of those places, these are rhapsodies based on the themes of Hungarian and Gypsy folk songs and dances are unique national-romantic poems. On the eve of the arrival of romanticism in England (the second half of the 18th century), all unusual, mysterious, strange and fantastic things (feelings, situations, adventures) that are considered an important element of poetry began to be expressed by the word romantic. In Germany at the end of the 18th century, and in France at the beginning of the 19th century, as well as in countries such as Italy, Poland, and Russia, romanticism came into use as the name of a literary trend different from classicism. Romanticism is the result of the non-enlightenment movement that swept all the countries of Europe. Dissatisfaction with the results of the Great French Revolution served as a social ground for the emergence of this trend. Sentiment against the way of life in the bourgeois society, selfishness and immorality of the members of the society, development in the fields of industry, politics and science caused new conflicts, awakened the feeling of striving for absolute ideals in the romantics. They dreamed not of partial improvement of life, but of complete elimination of all conflicts in it. In Romanticism, one of the means of expressing the conflict between ideal and reality is irony (A. Musse, G. Heine, etc.). Initially, irony meant the recognition of the idea that any historical reality is relative, but later it was saturated with the realization that romantic ideals will not be realized.

The representatives of romanticism drew fiction, folk tales, natural landscapes, past historical days, the life, customs and manners of distant peoples and countries into the image circle, against the colorless situations in society; they paid special attention to the depiction of great romantic passions and spiritual life. For this reason, the role and importance of religion, art and philosophy in romanticism increased to an unprecedented level. In France, the traditions of classicism have been preserved for a long time. 1886 at the beginning, 75-year-old Liszt goes to England, where Queen Victoria accepted by and excited by those who appreciate it is welcomed. Liszt, tired and feeling sick. He comes to Bayreuth from England for the

annual Hungarian Festival. That's it he died in the city on July 31, 1886, due to pneumonia.

Due to this, the penetration of Romanticism into French literature and art was difficult. Only in the 20s of the 19th century did Romanticism take its rightful place in French literature. The heritage of the Enlightenment era and the organic connection with the literary traditions of the past, interest in the current socio-political problems of the time are inseparable features of French romanticism.

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